

Artificial Intelligence: An Innovative Technology Towards Solving Insecurity Challenges in Nigeria

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Abstract

Nigeria is under siege by armed bandits especially Boko Haram. Sinister groups are operating in various guises that had left the military skeptical and agape. The challenges of insecurity, is a source of concern to many citizens hence the study is opting that Artificial Intelligence (AI) be adopted by the military command structure in their attempt to stop the menace. It is a purposive study that relies on Secondary sources mostly previous literature. Artificial Intelligence is the ability to create tools/solutions through human imaginations. It is service through the use of computers to enable robots and other machines facilitate, or mimic human intelligence. AI when effectively manipulated will without doubt provide opportunities for quick decision-making; create dominance that could reduce the serial killings perpetuated in the nation that is endowed with multiple natural resources. It will also assist in intelligence gathering, thereby enabling the State to be more proactive; programmed machines may do the surveillance jobs the military personnel are physically contending with now. Applying AI will reduce human casualties. In conclusion, the paper observed that despite the many benefits of AI, its applicability in Nigeria is abysmal. It is recommended that men in the security sector be regularly trained and their knowledge up dated. Funding research and technology must be seen as imperative. Above all, the citizens must be willing to cooperate with the security agents; such collaboration between AI and humans will help to surmount critical security challenges in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Innovation, Technology, Insecurity, Challenges.*

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Introduction

Nigeria is one country that had experienced its fair share of challenges regarding insecurity. No tribe in Nigeria be it Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo or Ijaw or any other section

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that had not suffered one form of setback nor infliction in terms of loss of life and property. The value of human life is almost worthless due to the nefarious activities of bandits (be they Boko Haram, Fulani Herdsmen, militia groups in the South East or the Niger Delta militants). From every indication, the volatile nature of the Nigerian state appears to be out of the control of the security agencies whose responsibility is to protect its citizens from both internal and external aggression. The aftermath of the present predicaments had also negatively affected the economy of the nation as the merger resources of the state are now expended mostly on fighting insurgency, banditry, kidnapping and other non-state actors. Furthermore, with the constant clashes between herdsmen and crop farmers, there is also serious food insecurity in the country which had resulted in to abject poverty and anxiety among its citizenry. This among other reasons is why the nation must look beyond the box to seek for ways and means of tackling its security challenges. In this position paper, the researchers seek to examine the place of artificial intelligence as an innovative technology to address this hydra-headed predicament inflicting the nation.

What is Artificial Intelligence?

Artificial intelligence referred mostly as (AI), which was first given its nomenclature (name) in 1956 at the Dartmouth conference; had become an integral part of man's everyday living (Nomerovskia, 2023). It is difficult to imagine any area of human endeavor where in artificial intelligence is not playing an important role.

Artificial intelligence as conceptualized by many authorities, is the ability to use manipulative machines or computer systems to mimic human intelligence in dealing with tasks that typically require human intelligence. Some of these tasks that machines could perform for instance are problem-solving and decision making (Ibrahim, 2023). Innovation means creating changes to assist humanity facilitate rapid progress and helping to transform technological processes. Innovation implies using new methods and skills to foster better and faster means of advancing human growth depending on substituting technology. AI is for the present and the future advancement of societies (Nsude, 2022). The researchers are amazed as to how commercial business centers are working efficiently today without security personnel opening gates or glass doors for customers. Merely approaching the door, the opens will open itself through the application of technology. Developed nations like China and Japan as well as the United State of America had started using robots to sell goods in stores. The world appears to be leaving Africa behind as there are presently cars without drivers operating using digital technologies. AI has helped humans' network with any part of the globe in terms of communications, warfare, and even in the medical fields. Today, in China, there are hospitals performing major services with robots instead of interacting physically with the medical personnel. AI had made it possible for humans and machines to collaborate more closely. In the field of agriculture for instance, robots now start farming activities from cultivation to harvesting and even to processing. The result or outcomes of this transformational possibilities are staggering and sensational (MasterCard foundation, 2024).

According to Congressional Research Service (CRS) reports as cited in Nsude (2022), AI is an artificial system designed to think or act like a human being doing wonders that, include cognitive architectures and neural networks. AI had perfected a set of techniques, including machine learning that is designed to approximate a cognitive task. Furthermore, AI is described as an artificial system designed to act rationally,

including an intelligent software agent or embodied robot that achieves goals using perception, planning, reasoning, learning, communicating, decision-making and acting. It is a software system design with the intention to mimic and model human intelligence.

AI deals with data and the use of robots too. Robot are powered machines capable of executing a set of actions by direct human control, computer control or a combination of both. At the minimum, it is comprised of a platform, software and power source (Department of Defense, as cited in CRS Report 2020). With AI, tools are designed and specifically manipulated to conduct intelligent assignments with greater speed and possibilities. AI is without doubt, one of the greatest innovations man had contemplated.

By implication, these definitions largely show that AI is a combination of machine learning and robots that are inbuilt with intelligence to act like humans. It is machine learning and robots given human characteristics. Although AI, machines, and robots can do a lot of activities and imbibe human behavior, they still cannot direct activities without direct human assistance. Despite the various roles which AI can play, according to Allen (2020), AI is yet to encompass the human level of intelligence across a broad range of tasks.

In review of the various responsibilities of AI especially with respect to security, world leaders like Vladimir Putin had spoken about the significance of AI to the security architect of nations. In his words “whoever becomes the leader in AI will be the ruler of the world” (Kania, 2017). Nations had invented birds with batteries to act as spies and report back intelligently sometimes with accurate graphic images. AI is a revolutionary trend that is dynamic and ever evolving.

AI as a “non-human intelligence program can perform specific tasks. It had revolutionized the world’s security architecture in many ways. AI supports humans in the collection of information and communication technologies (ICT) that mimic human intelligence to enable machines to facilitate jobs and assignments better, create greater efficiencies and drive economic growth among nations. It is the capacity of various machines to perform specific roles and task currently done by humans within the workplace and society in general (Arakpogun, E. O; Elsahn, Z; Olan, F., Elgahn, F. (2021).

As earlier mentioned, AI has a place in agriculture, banking, education, health, its reach and usefulness is still unfolding. It is estimated that by 2030, AI could contribute over 15 trillion dollars to the economy with more than 20% increase in the GDP of local economies as human and robots “work” in harmony to engineer solutions challenging the world (PWC, 2017).

Nigeria can use AI to Win the War against Insecurity

In a time like this, Nigeria can decide to adopt AI as a mechanism in addressing some of its security challenges. With AI the under listed solutions could be obtained:

1. AI technology could help autonomous operations, which could lead to more informed military operations, lead to more informed military decision-making, and increase the speed and scale of military actions (CRS Report, 2020).

2. As highlighted by Putin, whoever dominates in the field of AI will rule the world. Nigeria deserves this experience to stop issues of hijacking of trains and other essential service providers.

3. It can be incorporated quickly in to a number of intelligence gathering, surveillance and reconnaissance applications, as well as in logistics, cyberspace operation, information operation, command and control, semi-autonomous and autonomous vehicles, and lethal autonomous weapon systems.

There are chances that their application in the fight against Boko Haram will provide the needed response that could dislodge the insurgents from their enclaves. In intelligence operations, the application of AI will mean that there are more sources than ever from which to establish the truth (Allen & Tamiel, 2017). AI is expected to be particularly useful in intelligence due to the large data sets available for analysis (CRS discussion; Dr. Richard Linderman, 2017 as cited in CRS, 2020) Reports. For instance, the incorporation of computer vision and AI algorithms into intelligence collection cells that would comb through footages from uninhabited aerial vehicles and automatically identifying hostage activity for targeting, when achieved, could go a long way in exploring the forest areas that are the hideout of the Boko-Haram group and the armed herdsmen. In this capacity, AI will automate the work of human analysts who currently spend hours sifting through drone footages for actionable information, potentially freeing analysts to make more efficient and lonely decisions based on the data (Corrigan, 2017).

4. In the area of applying technology to reduce civilian causality, AI techniques are tremendous potentials for the military as well as help to prevent potential hazards. It is possible to envision scenarios in which AI can provide much more effective early identification in protecting civilians as well as combatants from enemy fire (for example, more precise targeting or minimizing collateral damage) (Hitchens, 2019). With regards to developing a more robust and rapid response to emergency scenarios, the key for the Nigerian Army will be adopting AI technologies and applying it to respond to Boko-Haram and Herdsmen attack that enhance survivability as well as isolating the negative impact that result from accidents, biological hazards, and natural disaster (Koester, 2020).

5. In the area of passive defense measurement, AI could assist taking proactive/precautionary steps to make it more difficult for hostile forces to locate and engage personal, assets, facilities, and various systems (such as communications). One could imagine the use of deep learning systems (machines that are programmed to discern when certain types of attacks are likely/imminent) conducting analysis quicker than could be expected by human monitoring and for reaction (Hoehn & Smagh, 2021). Other examples where deep learning systems could prove beneficial include cyber defense and electronic warfare attacks. In defense strategy, Autonomous Systems (AS) could be used to complement AI. In this respect, Autonomous Systems (AS) provides an advantage in defensive postures to select and engage incoming enemies, indirect fires (for e.g., mortars artillery, shells, and rockets). As Autonomous Systems (AS) designed to provide a rapid and robust “counter-battery” response against the origin of an attack provides commander with additional time to focus on second-and-third-order decisions given that the initial response to the attack was “automatically initiated with speed and accuracy (CRS Report, 2020). Israel uses this type of force in the protection of approaches with its iron dome defense systems (Clark, 2017).

6. In the area of logistics, AI can be used to reduce the spate of military aircraft crashes that the Nigeria military experience in its operations in enemy territory and sometimes in war free zones. Such crashes are the results of undetected faults. In this case, AI may have future utility in the field of military logistics. The Air Force, for example is beginning to use AI for predictive aircraft maintenance. Instead of making repairs when an aircraft breaks off in accordance with standardized fleet-wide maintenance schedules to the needs of individual aircraft (CRS, 2020).

7. Regarding the use of AI/AS in military operations, there are currently four capability areas envisioned for unmanned systems: battle space awareness, force application, protection and logistics (Colin & Clark, 2017). For example, the use of robots would mean that fewer troops would be needed to defend a certain piece of terrain (CRS, 2020). Robots also have the capability to operate for longer period of time without the human need for rest. As long as the command is issued, robots would continually act accordingly until a contrary directive is given.

8. Moreover, unarmed systems can operate in harsh and deadly environments (for example, chemical, biological, radiological or nuclear) with less degradation in capabilities. These and other instances provide an economy-of-force advantage that would allow army commanders the flexibility to allocate personnel to particular aspects of a battle plan). A likely example, interpretive or conceptual work that are not conducive to or appropriate for unmanned systems (Defense Innovation Board, 2019 & Tarrat, et al, 2019). An economy-of-force advantage from AI/AS would help address one of General Drin Ford's concerns, namely that 'the joint forces currently lacks sufficient capacity to meet all the combatant commands' requirement for force' (Defense Innovation Board, 2019).

9. AI has the potential to be integrated across a variety of applications, improving the so-called "internet of things" in which disparate devices are networked together to optimize performance (Ranger, 2018). In addition, many AI applications are dual-use, meaning they have both military and civil applications. For example, image recognition algorithm can be trained to recognizing cats in YouTube videos as well as terrorist activities in full motion videos captured by uninhabited aerial vehicles. In support of the foregoing, Allen & Taniel (2017) stated that future progress in AI has the potential to be a transformative national security technology, on a par with nuclear weapons, aircraft, computers, and biotechnologies. According to the authors, AI has led to significant changes in the strategy, organizations priorities and allocated resources of the US national security community. The use of AI will be at least equally impactful. Allen and Taniel, (2017), stated that advances in AI will affect national security by driving change in three areas: military superiority, information superiority and economic superiority. Three dimensions every nation requires to fortify its defense, security and sovereignty with.

In the area of military superiority, the application of AI in Nigeria will both enable new capabilities and make existing capabilities affordable to a broader range (Allen Taniel, 2017). For instance, commercially available, AI-enabled technology (such as long-range drone package delivery) may give weak states and non-state actors access to a type of long-range precision strike capacity. Many developed nations had relied on detective Closed Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras in the fight against various crimes like murder, surveillance in business centers and at individual homes. Public places especially entertainment/event centers are also carefully being monitored by cameras to the extent that there appears to be no hiding place for mischief makers. These unprecedented advantages no doubt will help Nigerian state mitigate her

insurmountable security challenges once conscious and dedicated effort is applied with sincerity of purpose.

Conclusion

In summary, military activities could be enhanced in risk management, communicating and maintaining the status of information among and across subordinated units, assessing progress towards accomplishing mission-related task and coordinating/controlling the employment of joint lethal capabilities (CRS Reports, 2020). This could boost efficiency in the military decision-making process. “Winning in the decision space is winning in the battle space” as emphasized by Samuel White in (Schwartz & Heidi, 2018).

It's beneficial in providing more timely, accurate and relevant intelligence that results in a more robust common operating picture across the joint forces, something that would provide a staff with the opportunity to keep commanders better apprised of developments in the battle space (Department of Defense, 2020).

It can assist automated analysis of volumes of daily Facebook posts by the so-called Islamic State and its sympathizers, looking for actionable intelligence that even the most robust team of humans could not possibly generate in a similarly efficient manner (Department of Defense, 2020). General Dun Ford has described these types of scenarios as the ability of commanders to “make decisions at the speed of relevance” (Chalfont, 2017).

On intelligence processing, AI is important in six categories of intelligence operations: (1) Planning and directing; collection, processing and exploitation, analysis and production, dissemination and integration, and evaluation and feedback (Smith, 2018). There by correcting band wagon effects during military operations. AI is really the way to solving Nigeria's security challenges with good political will and avoidance of corruption among the military brass and their cohorts.

Recommendations

The following recommendation may be relevant to assisting the security architecture of Nigeria.

1. Training and retraining of officers and men of the military especially in AI and other modern technologies is imperative in view of the multiple benefits of AI.
2. Adopting AI as a strategy of intelligence gathering will assist in curbing insurgency a great deal.
3. Government should not relent in funding technological approaches if the war on insecurity must be won.
4. The human beings must seriously collaborate and cooperate by been sincere to the course. Unless the behaviour and attitude of the mind is free of corruption, to salvage the nigerian state; it will be difficult to stop insurgency and banditry for the good of all citizens.
5. AI should be introduced early among children into the school curriculum right from the nursery/primary level. The funding and equipping of technological laboratories and workshop should be given priority by the governments at all levels.

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